

8T, QFT and GR – The Ace Equations

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Abstract:

By analyzing the three leading theories, two of the past century and the newborn 8T according to their leading equations, we can get a broad sense on the full picture in self. The paper is presented in a form of a mind-map as in that form, connections is easier to extract.

Introduction

References

- [1] O. Manor. "8 Theory – The Theory of Everything" In: (2021)
- [2] O. Manor. "8T, QFT and GR – Synthesis to GUT " In: (2021)
- [3] O. Manor. "8T and QFT Axiomatic Analysis" In: (2021)
- [4] O. Manor. "8T – The meaning of it all " In: (2021)